

MEET VIVIEN

Vivien Bonvin represented **Switzerland** at the IPT 2011, served as an organiser of the IPT 2013 and IPT 2014, and served as the **IPT President** in 2014-2017

Looking back, what first motivated you to join the International Physicists' Tournament?

If we speak about my year as a participant, honestly, my motivation was mainly the prospect of travelling abroad. The notion of competition around Physics problem was a concept completely new to me, and I simply followed along a friend of mine who saw this tournament as an opportunity to visit Moscow and needed to assemble a team as a pretext. But then, even though we weren't definitely participating for the beauty of Physics itself, we still wanted to be sufficiently prepared in order not to look like complete donkeys. And that is where, for me, the magic happened. This wasn't yet another of these boring lecture or pointless exercise session that my bachelor degree was full of - finally there was something exciting and joyful about applying what I painstakingly learned in the past years.

My team and I had great fun participating that week, and even though we went with zero results expectations, we managed to finish on the podium. We came back to Switzerland supercharged, then motivated a bunch of other schoolmates to participate in the 4th edition the following year. They also enjoyed the experience a lot, and one of them - with a more adventurous mindset than the rest of us - proposed to organize the 5th edition in Switzerland, at EPFL. Once again I ended up simply following along, and found myself on the organizational side this time, as both Treasurer of the Local Organizing Committee (LOC) and responsible of tracking the team scores during the tournament.

This is the time where I discovered that there was a lot of pleasure to be found in organizing things. The 5th edition of the tournament went so well that I signed up for being part of the 6th edition organisation, still at EPFL, this time as President of the LOC. Things went very well again (fun anecdote, the night at the end of that edition is the only one in my life when I blacked out - I've never been that tired - and just woke up very confused in a bed that wasn't mine). At that point the IPT really started to be a proper international event, and needed a more long-term piloting body; the International Organizing Committee (IOC) was then created, and I took its Presidency for the next 3 and a half years. I have been lucky enough during my time to be supported by groups of people in the IOC and LOCs way more skilled and visionary than me, who eventually made the tournament what it is today - an enduring competition well recognized internationally, where participants dedicate an amount of time and skill I would have deemed insane during my university days..

Vivien giving president address at the IPT 2017

Which IPT problem, debate, or experience left the strongest impression on you – and why?

At age 21, like many people at that time of life I wasn't necessarily very comfortable in my own skin. Specifically, besides being relatively decent at solving equations - hence me studying Physics at the time - I wasn't clear about what my professional strengths were. So, when I was called forth during the 1st day of the selective Physics fights, first of my team to defend my solution of a weird problem (I had to devise a way to orient a spaceship whose commands were broken, in the vicinity of a pulsar), without any knowledge of what a Physics fight will look like, well I just went in with a "f**k it, smile and wave, they won't eat you" mentality. It turned out okay - I got graded six or seven, I don't really remember. Yet at the end of the fight, one jury member, a Russian professor with one of those very serious faces only Russian professors can produce, came to me and told me very solemnly that my presentation was one of the nicest he's seen in a while. And to highlight his words he gave me a pin with h nu symbols - the ones from the Planck relation. That was a really cool gesture.

Where has your journey taken you since your IPT days professionally?

I've spend six years doing Astrophysics; 4 as a PhD, 2 as a postdoc. I have been lucky enough once again to have great people around me - notably a well-recognized and helpful supervisor, thanks to whom I could take part in the golden years of an equally helpful international collaboration. We set out to measure how fast the Universe expands - something that keeps Cosmologists and Astrophysicists busy (understand: at each other's throat) since more than a century and awarded a Nobel prize in 2011. It turned out that our most precise measurement agreed quite nicely with said measurement from the Nobel laureate, and rather disagree with the 300+ scientist collaboration who recently measured a different value. The luck of the draw, as well as the above-mentioned helpful supervisor designated me as the PhD student to first author that paper. That gave me quite a lot of fame overnight and I got invited to a bunch of conferences, most notably the 69th Lindau Nobel Laureate meeting, where

I presented my work in front of a bunch of Nobel laureates - at which point to keep my cool I reminded myself of the Russian professor with the pin's. I also got a few

encouraging prizes for my thesis, and got a nice traction in the community,

meaning, if nothing else, that I had a good chance ahead of me to get a second postdoc in any well-known university.

Vivien at the IPT 2011

Yet to the dismay of my advisor, I decided in 2019 to exit academia. Reasons are aplenty, and I can mention the poor state in which academia

is: a broken system of citation to measure one's efficiency, the ultra-high importance of politics, needing a good network to get oneself a chance to succeed, and obviously the fact that the vast majority of the labs are headed by professors with zero knowledge in people and projects management, and no accountability whatsoever when they fuck-up someone's career - which luckily wasn't my case but I've heard many horror stories. Point being, I wasn't that enthralled by academia as a workplace.

But most of all, I realised during my time in academia, and that includes my IPT years, that what I really liked was coding.

Despite almost no formal education in code (I am the one responsible for the infamous IPT connect app tracking the tournament scores, something that I hope has been rewritten by now!), I wanted to get close to real software development. And so, I started to apply for Data Science positions.

I eventually found something in a company now called Vyntra, that develops software solutions to prevent fraud and money laundering in financial institutions. I started there as a Data Scientist, with quite a lot of freedom to design algorithm to prevent fraud, and implement them into the software suite - right what I wanted. I had a blast, and long story short, I took more and more responsibilities over the years, became more important in the decisional process, graduated quite fast from regular Data Scientist to Senior, then Data Architect, then Lead, and finally now acting Head of Data Science. I am now managing a team of 6 bright individuals, and although I am not coding much anymore I still participate in most of the design discussions, which is enough to scratch the itch. Besides, being in a leadership position is a lot of meetings and spending a significant fraction of my working life living in powerpoints, which sounds way more awful than it really is. I do now believe that any successful organization, whether in academia, public or professional, can only work well if the people in it coordinate well, and are given the means to achieve their potential. My years in Physics make me frame this as optimizing the flow of information between all layers within the company, and clear a path of least resistance for my colleague to achieve their objectives.

How did participating in the IPT shape your approach to research, teamwork, or communication in your later studies or career?

The largest impact has been on the communication aspect. A layman might believe that since we're dealing with the common language of equations and, quite often, hard observational facts, scientists would always understand each other almost instantaneously. As a naïve student who never left his university, I was thinking more or less the same. Participating in the IPT was the first eye-opening experience: we might be talking about the same problem, with the same tools and common language, we might be geographically and even socially not that far apart, understanding and convincing each other is hard! Specifically, it cannot be done with dry math alone, no matter how correct they are; If I want to convince someone to agree with me, up to the point to have them agree that I am right (and they might be wrong), I need to build a narrative, I need to hook them with a story.

After a master in Physics, I continued with a PhD in Astrophysics, 2 years of postdoc and then I moved in the private sector as a Data Scientist. All along that journey, I honed my storytelling skills: what to tell (and to whom), when to be dry, when to be bullish, when to be dramatic. It served me a lot, and keeps being one my strengths today.

What's one skill or lesson from the IPT that you still find yourself using today?

I am now a long time away from this first "public" presentation I gave in Moscow in 2011 for the 3rd IPT edition, but quite often when I present nowadays the feeling is the same: I can only guess my audience's expectations, they are often way more seniors than I am, and I am pretty sure they will contradict me at some point, if not for a good reason, just to show that they are the seniors in the room. And quite often I say to myself: "this is the same setup than 15 years ago, smile and wave, and tell them a story". I worked quite well so far, there are no reasons it drastically changes now!

